

Pilot Testing a Principles Aligned Institutionally-Contextualised (PAI-C) Introductory RDM Training for HDR Candidates

An implementation project for the Institutional Underpinnings Program

Project summary report

Bond University, University of New South Wales, University of Sydney

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About the Institutional Underpinnings Program

In partnership with 25 Australian universities, we created a jointly-agreed Research Data Management Framework for Institutions for the management, sharing, retention and disposal of research data. Each partner university conducted projects to validate and test an aspect of the framework in their local contexts. This is a report on one of the projects.

More information

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).

View the [Research Data Management Framework for Institutions](#).

Project Summary

Bond University, the University of New South Wales and the University of Sydney undertook a joint project to develop and pilot test a Research Data Management (RDM) introductory educational/training experience for Higher Degree Research (HDR) candidates that targeted minimum RDM training outcomes/competencies, and contains the respective university's materials/information on policies, processes and systems. Three university-contextualised versions were produced and pilot tested as part of this project.

This project used the minimum RDM competencies identified in the Institutional Underpinnings (IU) [RDM Framework](#) element, "Support, Training and Guidance", to backward design an RDM introductory educational/training experience for new HDR candidates (see Wiggins & McTighe, 2011). The experience is Principles Aligned Institutionally-Contextualised (PAI-C) as (1) high-level RDM principles, or RDM best practice, are implicit within the identified RDM competencies (e.g., the need to consider secure data storage/access), and (2) the experience contains university-contextualised materials/information.

The PAI-C experience drew from a user-centric participatory design approach to develop the RDM training, which brings users to the fore by giving them a voice in the design and development of tools, environments and systems that serve them (DiSalvo, Bonsignore, Yip, & DiSalvo, 2017; Spinuzzi, 2005). Inputs from HDRs, internal university stakeholders and IU members were elicited throughout the process through focus groups and consultation sessions to ensure that the PAI-C experience is useful for all parties.

The pilot PAI-C introductory RDM experience has eight sections and takes approximately 1.5 hours to complete:

- Section 1: Overview of RDM and Expectations
- Section 2: Overview of Data Classification
- Section 3: Data Classification Case Studies
- Section 4: University-supported Data Platforms
- Section 5: Data Handling Case Study –Part I (Secure Storage & Backing-up)
- Section 6: Data Handling Case Study –Part II (Data Retention)
- Section 7: RDM Planning (Starting an RDMP)
- Section 8: Conclusion (Reiterating key RDM expectations and next steps)

The PAI-C experience was pilot tested across Bond University, the University of New South Wales and the University of Sydney. The pilot testing was deployed in three different Learning Management Systems successfully, and with HDR candidates (n = 69) across various backgrounds and research disciplines.

Resulting Improvements

This PAI-C introductory RDM training/educational experience will form part of the overall RDM support provided at each of the universities. It is currently planned for the PAI-C experience to be made available to Higher Degree Research (HDR) candidates across the pilot testing sites. For Bond University and the University of Sydney, this will allow the two universities to roll out and track baseline RDM training at scale for HDR candidates. For the University of New South Wales, the PAI-C experience is considered an update to its existing RDM training for HDR candidates in the areas of data handling and retention.

Next Steps

The preliminary findings from the pilot testing across three different universities show that PAI-C has the potential to be adapted for different contexts, and deliver common/baseline actionable objectives for HDR candidates to enact. Through the process of contextualising the PAI-C experience with each university's RDM materials/information, it also allowed the universities to determine if their RDM policies, processes and systems are aligned to deliver common/baseline actionable objectives.

As such, this suggests that if there are resources to contextualise the PAI-C experience for more Australian institutions, sufficient momentum and critical mass could be garnered to establish a common baseline understanding of RDM across institutions, which in turn will facilitate cross institutional management of data (e.g. when researchers move between institutions, and collaborate across institutions).

Further work might also explore to see if PAI-C experience can be adapted for use with research staff.

Project Outputs

Links to PAI-C demonstration content are available via DRESA. The full content is available on request, follow the links for details.

<https://dresa.org.au/materials/principles-aligned-institutionally-contextualised-pai-c-rdm-training>

The full PAI-C content is available in a storyboard format, ready for adapting to any delivery mechanism or learning technology, and includes instructions on how to contextualise implementation at different institutions. Within the storyboard format two versions are available, the principles-based core content ("principles version") and an implementation example ("UNSW version"). The PAI-C storyboard is designed primarily for developing an online asynchronous training experience that can be deployed at scale.

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).